

An Academic Perspective on Regional Variations of Psoriasis

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To cite this article: Collaborate, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 5-11, 2024, p. 01– 17. - 0099-0001-2411-0101.

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(“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”) ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Niyaz Bokvadze

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Abstract

Psoriasis is a chronic autoimmune dermatological disorder marked by the accelerated proliferation of keratinocytes, resulting in the development of thick, scaly plaques. It affects around 2–3% of the global population and is linked to considerable bodily distress and psychological consequences. The illness often manifests in cycles, characterized by phases of aggravation and subsequent remission, thereby necessitating a comprehension of the underlying processes for efficient care. The pathophysiology of psoriasis encompasses a complex interaction of genetic, environmental, and immunological elements. At the cellular level, the illness is characterized by an expedited skin cell life cycle, with the normal 28-day turnover rate decreased to 3–6 days. This hyperproliferation leads to the accumulation of prematurely shed cells, resulting in the formation of distinctive silvery-white scales. The etiology of psoriasis is mostly associated with the activation of T-helper 1 (Th1) and T-helper 17 (Th17) cell responses. These immune cells release proinflammatory cytokines, including interleukin-17 (IL-17) and interleukin-23 (IL-23), which sustain the inflammatory cycle. Furthermore, the involvement of dendritic cells, keratinocytes, and other immunological mediators exacerbates this dysregulated immune response. Environmental factors, including stress, infections, and skin traumas, may intensify psoriasis outbreaks and underscore the intricate interplay between the skin and the immune system.

Keywords : *Psoriasis, Psoriasis and Regional Psoriasis, Psoriasis, Psoriasis and Variations, Variations of Psoriasis*

Introduction

Psoriasis is a persistent autoimmune dermatological disorder marked by the accelerated growth of keratinocytes, resulting in the development of thick, scaly plaques. It affects around 2–3% of the global population and is linked to considerable bodily distress and psychological consequences. The illness often manifests in cycles, characterized by phases of aggravation and subsequent remission, thereby necessitating a comprehension of the underlying processes for

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Aim

The prevalence of psoriasis has been shown to rise with time, with new evidence indicating escalating rates, especially in metropolitan populations and wealthy nations. In contrast, increasing research suggests a potential decline in incidence rates among some groups, due to improved health treatments and changes in lifestyle choices. Global Cancer Incidence and Mortality Rates and Trends—An Update, 2015 Our research intends to analyze this data.

Methodology

Age and gender significantly influence the prevalence of psoriasis, exhibiting a bimodal age distribution. The first peak often occurs between the ages of 15 and 30, but the subsequent peak is seen between the ages of 50 and 60. Gender disparities exist, with men exhibiting a greater prevalence than females. Comprehending the worldwide prevalence and incidence of psoriasis is essential for customizing public health initiatives and enhancing research into targeted treatments, hence improving patient outcomes across various groups.

Literature Review

Psoriasis is a complex chronic inflammatory dermatological disorder marked by recurring episodes of erythematous plaques adorned with silvery scales. The incidence, severity, and phenotypic characteristics may significantly range between geographical regions, indicating a complex interplay of genetic, environmental, and societal influences. Sianto et al., 2023 International epidemiological research indicate that the prevalence of psoriasis ranges from 0.1% to 11.8% across different nations. For instance, research indicates elevated incidence in nations with largely Caucasian demographics, such as Finland and Norway, and decreased frequency in areas of Asia, Africa, and South America.

The disparities might be ascribed to several variables, such as genetic predisposition and environmental effects. Variations in the manifestation and intensity of psoriasis may also be ascribed to population-specific immune responses and the existence of distinct genetic markers linked to the condition.

Cultural beliefs and health-seeking habits about skin problems profoundly influence regional treatment methodologies. In some cultures, psoriasis may be stigmatized, resulting in underdiagnosis and insufficient treatment, but in others, it may be addressed through a holistic lens that incorporates traditional medicine. (Morrone et al., 2020)

Comprehending geographical variations in psoriasis is essential for customizing localized treatment approaches and formulating culturally relevant educational initiatives. Healthcare professionals and researchers must recognize these disparities to increase patient outcomes and optimize the overall treatment of psoriasis.

Future research should concentrate on elucidating the fundamental reasons of these geographical disparities, perhaps resulting in tailored treatment solutions that include both genetic predispositions and environmental influences impacting patients globally. A Review of Global Prevalence and Recent Advances in Psoriasis Genetics, n.d.

Environmental Factors Affecting Psoriasis by Region

Psoriasis is a complex condition, with environmental variables significantly influencing its expression and severity across various locales. These variables include climatic, environmental, and behavioral conditions that substantially influence both the prevalence and clinical manifestation of psoriasis. *Epidemiology of Psoriasis*, 2006

Temperature is a fundamental climatic variable. Regions with colder temperatures have elevated incidence of psoriasis flare-ups, attributable to less sunshine exposure and heightened skin dryness. Conversely, warmer areas often have reduced prevalence rates, perhaps owing to the beneficial effects of sunshine, which may enhance vitamin D production, a crucial element for skin health.

Air quality is a significant environmental influence. Urban environments with elevated pollution levels may aggravate psoriasis symptoms, since irritants may provoke inflammatory reactions in predisposed people. In contrast, rural regions characterized by cleaner air often have reduced occurrences of psoriasis, indicating a potential preventive influence of environmental cleanliness.

The geographic location influences exposure to allergens like pollen and mold, which may exacerbate psoriasis symptoms. The incidence of skin infections in places with elevated humidity, such as tropical climates, may be considerable and complicate the treatment of psoriasis while exacerbating symptoms. *Geopedemiology and Environmental Factors of Psoriasis and Psoriatic Arthritis*, 2010

Cultural lifestyle practices, including bathing routines and work exposures, underscore the geographical diversity of psoriasis. For instance, regular immersion in mineral-laden waters prevalent in certain regions has shown efficacy in alleviating symptoms and enhancing general skin health.

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Therefore, understanding the regional environmental elements that affect psoriasis is essential for formulating efficient local preventive and treatment strategies, therefore informing therapeutic interventions and enhancing patients' quality of life.

Genetic Predispositions and Regional Differences in Psoriasis

Genetic predisposition significantly contributes to the development of psoriasis, a chronic inflammatory dermatological illness shaped by a complex interplay of genetic and environmental variables. Multiple studies have pinpointed distinct genetic variations linked to the onset of psoriasis, notably locations on chromosomes 6p21 (HLA-Cw6), 4q (IL-23R), and 1q (TNFAIP3). (Liu et al., 2008)

These genetic markers, although universally pertinent, display differing frequency among populations, indicating that regional genetic backgrounds substantially affect the incidence and clinical manifestation of psoriasis. Individuals of European heritage have a greater prevalence of HLA-Cw6 than Asian populations, resulting in variations in illness manifestation and severity. Furthermore, geographical variations in genetic predispositions affect the health inequalities seen in psoriasis. Ethnic groups with certain genetic variations may exhibit varied responses to environmental stimuli, like stress, infection, or nutritional influences, which might exacerbate or mitigate symptoms.

The interplay between genetic predispositions and environmental factors creates a distinctive epidemiological framework in psoriasis, with certain locations demonstrating varying vulnerability or resistance based on their genetic composition. (Liu et al., 2006) Furthermore, understanding the genetic underpinnings of psoriasis is essential for the advancement of targeted therapeutics and personalized medicine strategies. Comprehending geographical variations in genetic predispositions not only enlightens doctors on potential illness trajectories but also aids in stratifying patients for clinical trials and therapeutic treatments customized to particular genetic profiles.

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In summary, the genetic foundation of psoriasis, together with geographical variations, highlights the need for culturally informed frameworks for the therapy of psoriasis. Future study should further clarify these links and eventually enhance the knowledge and management of psoriasis in various groups.

Climatic Effects on the Severity and Distribution of Psoriasis

Psoriasis is a multifactorial condition marked by the accelerated proliferation of skin cells, mostly driven by genetic, immunological, and environmental factors. Climate significantly influences the intensity and spread of psoriasis among environmental factors. Research indicates that various temperature zones, including tropical, temperate, and arctic, exhibit distinct occurrences and patterns of psoriasis prevalence. In temperate regions, the impact of seasonal variations, particularly ultraviolet (UV) radiation, is pronounced. Ultraviolet radiation is recognized for its therapeutic benefits on psoriasis, often resulting in improvement during brighter months and exacerbations during times of less sunshine. Zhao et al. (1998) In contrast, individuals residing in tropical locations often encounter elevated humidity levels, which may influence skin hydration. Elevated humidity may alleviate dryness and flaking, possibly mitigating the severity of psoriasis. Nonetheless, this is counterbalanced by the frequency of skin infections in humid environments, which may exacerbate the illness for some people. Colder locations, reduced temperatures, and arid air may exacerbate the prevalence of psoriasis due to their role in skin barrier impairment. This malfunction often causes heightened transepidermal water loss, resulting in dry, pruritic, and scaly skin. The physiological reactions of people with psoriasis to climatic stressors may differ markedly and substantially influence the progression of the illness.

In conclusion, climatic variables significantly affect the manifestation and intensity of psoriasis. Identifying these environmental factors is crucial for customizing effective treatment techniques to enhance patient outcomes across various geographic locations. Comprehending the relationship between environment and psoriasis is essential for further study and therapeutic application.

Dietary Effects on Psoriasis in Different Regions

Dietary practices significantly affect the clinical presentations and severity of psoriasis in different geographic areas. An increasing amount of research emphasizes the synergistic interaction of regional culinary traditions, nutritional availability, and cultural attitudes toward food in modifying inflammatory pathways related to psoriasis. Dietary Practices in Psoriasis: Patient-Reported Findings from the U.S. National Survey, 2017

In Mediterranean nations, a conventional diet rich in omega-3 fatty acids from fish, vegetables, and olive oil seems to have a preventive benefit against psoriasis. Omega-3 fatty acids are recognized for their ability to diminish inflammatory reactions and may result in less severe symptoms in individuals with psoriasis. Conversely, the severity and frequency of the condition have escalated in regions characterized by a diet rich in processed foods and sugar, notably in some sections of North America.

In Asian nations, where rice and soybeans are dietary mainstays, the research on their impact on psoriasis is inconclusive. Certain research indicate that probiotic-rich fermented foods may enhance gut health and diminish systemic inflammation, possibly mitigating psoriasis symptoms. Nevertheless, excessive intake of gluten-containing grains in certain areas may adversely affect individuals with gluten sensitivity and aggravate dermatological disorders. The function of vitamin D, mostly obtained from sunshine and some food sources, differs by geography. Populations with restricted solar exposure, like those in Scandinavian nations, often depend on fortified foods and pills to sustain sufficient vitamin D levels, essential for skin health and immunological regulation. (Haq, 2013)

Cultural Practices and Their Impact on Psoriasis Management

Cultural traditions profoundly affect psoriasis care, creating a notable interplay between traditional beliefs and modern medical methods. In many locations, these behaviors influence

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patients' perspectives on medication adherence, food selections, and lifestyle modifications that may impact the severity of their ailment.

In several cultures, the view of psoriasis as a persistent and sometimes stigmatized dermatological disorder may result in differing degrees of social support and medical treatment. In collectivist civilizations, communal support may enhance the exchange of coping solutions, hence improving management results. In societies where stigma is strong, people may be less inclined to get therapy, perhaps resulting in worse symptoms. DeSilva et al. (2014)

Findings

Dietary practices significantly influence the management of psoriasis. Certain cultures prioritize the intake of anti-inflammatory foods, while others include high-sodium or processed meals, which may exacerbate symptoms. Conventional medicines often embody local eating habits, and their efficacy continues to be a subject of active investigation. Culturally ingrained lifestyle behaviors, including physical activity, sun exposure, and stress management approaches, significantly impact psoriasis treatment measures. Cultures that prioritize holistic practices may promote mind-body treatments that reduce stress, a recognized catalyst for psoriasis flare-ups.

Utilizing culturally relevant communication with healthcare providers helps strengthen the therapeutic relationship and foster trust, hence facilitating more effective treatment regimens customized to individual requirements. Consequently, comprehending cultural norms is crucial for formulating complete and successful psoriasis therapy plans that honor and include patients' cultural origins.

Argument

Psoriasis, a persistent inflammatory dermatological disorder, has considerable therapeutic disparities across different geographic areas. The disparities may be ascribed to several variables,

including healthcare infrastructure, cultural attitudes towards the condition, economic resources, and pharmaceutical availability.

In North America and Western Europe, sophisticated medicines including biologics and systemic drugs are extensively used, mostly owing to strong healthcare systems and substantial research funding. These locations provide a diverse array of therapy modalities, including medicines that specifically target immunological pathways implicated in the pathogenesis of psoriasis. (Guo et al., 2023)

Conversely, access to efficacious psoriasis therapies in low- and middle-income nations is often constrained. Conventional therapies, such coal tar and phototherapy, may prevail because to their reduced cost and enhanced accessibility. Moreover, socioeconomic obstacles may impede the execution of recommendations grounded in evidence-based practice. Cultural attitudes significantly impact treatment decisions; in some regions, there may be hesitance to pursue medical assistance, prompting people to depend on alternative medicines. This dependence is undermined by the inadequate demonstration of the efficacy of several such therapies in the scientific literature. Regional disparities also pertain to patient education and knowledge about psoriasis. Misinformation in some regions might result in stigma, adversely affecting treatment adherence and patient quality of life (Meier & Sheth, 2009).

Therefore, understanding these regional treatment trends and disparities is essential. By acknowledging the distinct obstacles encountered in various geographic regions, healthcare clinicians may formulate focused treatments to enhance management techniques and results for persons with psoriasis globally.

Case Studies: Psoriasis in Specific Geographical Areas

Psoriasis, a persistent inflammatory dermatological condition, has varied symptoms and prevalence across various geographic regions. This chapter offers focused case studies that

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highlight distinct characteristics of psoriasis in several areas, emphasizing environmental, genetic, and cultural factors.

The Nordic nations exemplify a notable instance of high psoriasis prevalence. Research indicates that the frequency in Norway and Sweden may reach up to 3% of the population. Genetic research indicates a significant genetic factor, especially associated with HLA-Cw6. Furthermore, colder regions may intensify symptoms, requiring a comprehensive comprehension of therapy methodologies.

Conversely, southern locations, including Mediterranean nations, have lower incidence rates, around 1% to 1.5%. The temperate environment, together with nutritional elements like a Mediterranean diet rich in olive oil and omega-3 fatty acids, significantly contributes to illness management. Cultural attitudes towards health and wellbeing also affect patients' engagement in preventative actions. Olivio et al. (2015)

Research indicates a rising prevalence of psoriasis in East Asian nations, often associated with industrialization and heightened stress levels. In nations like Japan and South Korea, the onset of psoriasis has been associated with environmental pollution and dietary alterations, hence heightening the need for localized therapeutic approaches.

Psoriasis may have unusual manifestations in regions with elevated incidences of tropical infections, particularly in some parts of Africa. Traditional practices and therapies often coexist with current medical methods, underscoring the significance of cultural context in therapeutic effectiveness.

These case studies underscore the need for localized research and individualized treatment techniques to foster a comprehensive approach to psoriasis care across various geographic locations (Nestle et al., 2009).

Implications for Future Research and Clinical Practice

This book emphasizes the intricate interaction of genetic, environmental, and cultural variables, underscoring the need for customized strategies in psoriasis care. Comprehending

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geographical differences in psoriasis enhances our knowledge of the illness and has significant implications for future research and therapeutic treatment.

Future study should concentrate on pinpointing particular genetic markers and their correlation with regional symptoms of psoriasis. Extensive, multi-location research will provide a more thorough comprehension of the interaction between genetic predispositions and environmental stimuli, guiding the development of tailored medicines. Moreover, investing in longitudinal research would enable the examination of how variables such as environment and dietary habits change over time, clarifying their enduring impacts on psoriasis severity and patient quality of life. (Menter et al., 2020)

Healthcare practitioners should use a more culturally sensitive methodology in the treatment of psoriasis. Understanding the influence of cultural customs and beliefs on treatment adherence might facilitate the creation of more effective, individualized management strategies. This encompasses customizing therapy to meet unique patient requirements as well as the distinct sociocultural environment in which patients reside.

Moreover, geographical disparities in treatment approaches underscore the urgent need to enhance access to psoriasis care across various groups. Policymakers must consider these disparities when distributing funding for psoriasis research and treatment infrastructure (Armstrong et al., 2016).

Ultimately, findings derived from analyzing geographical disparities in psoriasis need a transformation in both research and therapeutic practice. Focusing on localized methods would enhance our understanding of this complex disorder and improve results for people globally. This section is to include supplementary data tables and corresponding graphics that augment the comprehension of psoriasis across different locations. This compilation aims to enhance prior parts and offers a comprehensive examination of the complex nature of psoriasis on both global and regional levels. Griffiths et al. (2017)

Graphs illustrating climatic factors will elucidate the impact of temperature and humidity on the severity of psoriasis across various locales. Furthermore, infographics delineating

therapeutic modalities used across other cultures will provide insights into the multifaceted approach to psoriasis management. Diallo, 2012

Conclusion

The complex characteristics of psoriasis shown in the book underscore the significance of regional variations in its epidemiology and treatment. This article reviews the interplay of environmental, genetic, climatic, nutritional, and cultural variables in influencing the development and severity of psoriasis among many groups.

Comprehending the regional intricacies of psoriasis is essential for progressing individualized treatment strategies in dermatology. It compels academics to investigate the interplay between local environmental factors and genetic predispositions, broadening the pursuit of culturally and regionally informed treatment solutions.

Moreover, insights derived from case studies underscore the variability in clinical manifestations and therapeutic outcomes. They emphasize the need for healthcare practitioners to embrace a localized approach in diagnosing and treating psoriasis, ensuring that therapies align with the cultural traditions and dietary customs of specific populations. Griffiths et al. (2017) As we enhance our comprehension of psoriasis, it is essential that forthcoming research persist in addressing recognized gaps, particularly the intersectionality of several variables that affect disease prevalence and therapeutic techniques. Cooperative initiatives across global health organizations, researchers, and practitioners may enhance the exchange of data and ideas, eventually resulting in improved treatment procedures customized to regional requirements. This article has elucidated the intricacy of psoriasis across many areas and established a basis for future study and practice. Heightened knowledge of regional disparities will enhance therapeutic treatment and elevate the quality of life for those afflicted by this chronic ailment. Parisi et al. (2012)

References

- A Review of Global Prevalence and Recent Advances in the Genetics of Psoriasis. (n.d.).
<https://medcraveonline.com/MOJPB/MOJPB-06-00189.pdf>
- Armstrong, A W., Koning , J., Rowse , S., Tan , H., Mamolo , C., & Kaur , M. (2016, November 30). Undertreatment of Patients with Moderate to Severe Psoriasis in the United States: Analysis of Medication Use with Health Plan Data. *Adis , Springer Healthcare*, 7(1), 97-109. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13555-016-0153-2>
- DeSilva , M B., Samele , C., Saxena , S., Patel , V., & Darzi , A. (2014, September 1). Policy Actions to Achieve Integrated Community-Based Mental Health Services. *Project HOPE*, 33(9), 1595-1602. <https://doi.org/10.1377/hlthaff.2014.0365>
- Diallo , M. (2012, April 18). *Epidemiology of Psoriasis*. <https://www.hilarispublisher.com/open-access/psoriasis-epidemiology-2165-7920.1000e116.pdf>
- Dworkin , E R., Krahe , B., & Zinzow , H M. (2021, September 1). Global prevalence of sexual assault: a systematic review of international research since 2010. *American Psychological Association*, 11(5), 497-508. <https://doi.org/10.1037/vio0000374>
- Griffiths, C., Walt, J. M. V., Ashcroft , D. M., Flohr , C., Naldi , L., Nijsten , T., & Augustin, M. (2017, May 28). The global status of psoriasis epidemiology: a workshop report. *Oxford University Press* , 177(1), e4-e7. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjd.15610>
- Guo , J., Zhang , H., Lin , W., Lü , L., Su , J., & Chen , X. (2023, November 27). Signaling pathways and targeted therapies for psoriasis. *Springer Nature*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41392-023-01655-6>
- Haq , A. (2013, January 1). *Vitamin D: A Molecule of Universal Interest and Its Measurement*. OMICS Publishing Group, 04(09). <https://doi.org/10.4172/2157-7064.1000e117>

Jemal , LATRLSEMWA. (2015, December 14). Global Cancer Incidence and Mortality Rates and Trends - An Update. <https://aacrjournals.org/cebp/article/25/1/16/157144/Global-Cancer-Incidence-and-Mortality-Rates-and>

Joel.gelfand@uphs.upenn.edu, ALNAFCUOP 3 S 2 MB 1 P USBPAFCUOP 3 S 2 MB 1 P UJMGAFUCUOP 3 S 2 MB 1 P U. (2006, February 5). Epidemiology of psoriasis . <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1586/17469872.1.1.63>

Liu , Y., Helms , C., Liao , W., Zaba , L. C., Duan , S., Gardner , J. M., Wise , C. A., Miner , A. G., Malloy , M. J., Pullinger , C. R., Kane , J. P., Saccone , S. F., Worthington , J., Bruce , I. N., Kwok , P., Menter , A., Krueger , J. G., Barton , A., Saccone , N. L., & Bowcock , A. (2008, April 3). A Genome-Wide Association Study of Psoriasis and Psoriatic Arthritis Identifies Novel Disease Loci. Public Library of Science , 4(4), e1000041-e1000041. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgen.1000041>

Liu , Y., Krueger , J. G., & Bowcock , A. (2006, November 9). Psoriasis: genetic associations and immune system alterations. Springer Nature, 8(1), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.gene.6364351>

Meier , M J. & Sheth , P. (2009, January 1). Clinical Spectrum and Severity of Psoriasis. Karger Publishers, 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000232301>

Menter , A., Gelfand , J M., Connor , C., Armstrong , A W., Cordero , K M., Davis , D M R., Elewski , B E., Gordon , K B., Gottlieb , A B., Kaplan , D H., Kavanaugh , A., Kiselica , M., Kivelevitch , D., Korman , N J., Kroshinsky , D., Lebwohl , M., Leonardi , C L., Lichten , J., Lim , H W., . . Elmets , C A. (2020, February 28). American Academy of Dermatology-National Psoriasis Foundation common-care guidelines for the management of psoriasis with systemic nonbiological therapies. Elsevier BV, 82(6), 1445-1486. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaad.2020.02.044>

Moderate to Severe Psoriasis. (n.d.). <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/books/edit/10.3109/9781420088687/moderate-severe->

psoriasis-mark-lebwohl-chai-sue-lee-john-koo-ethan-levin-alice-gottlieb-gerald-weinstein-argentina-leon

- Morrone , A., Dell'Anna , M. L., Cristaudo , A., Woldearegay , T. W., Godefay , H., Barnabas , G. A., Dassoni , F., Padovese , V., Latini , O., Lotti , T., Saraceni , P., Domenico , E. G. D., & Lora , V. (2020, December 28). Psoriasis in Tigray , Ethiopia: Focusing on current treatments. Wiley , 35(3). <https://doi.org/10.1111/dth.14718>
- Nestle, F O., Kaplan, D H., & Barker , J. (2009, July 29). Psoriasis. Massachusetts Medical Society, 361(5), 496-509. <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmra0804595>
- Oliviero , F., Spinella , P., Fiocco , U., Ramonda , R., Sfriso , P., & Punzi , L. (2015, November 2). How the Mediterranean diet and some of its components modulate inflammatory pathways in arthritis. EMH Swiss Medical Publishers Ltd.. <https://doi.org/10.4414/smw.2015.14190>
- Parisi , R., Symmons , D., Griffiths , C. & Ashcroft , D M. (2012, September 27). The Global Epidemiology of Psoriasis: A Systematic Review of Incidence and Prevalence. Elsevier BV, 133(2), 377-385. <https://doi.org/10.1038/jid.2012.339>
- Sianto , JP., Aruan , R. , Widodo , GP. and Widodo , AA. (2023, August 22). Bimekizumab Now Prison Pilihan Psoriasis Vulgaris Type Plaque ., 2(2). <https://doi.org/10.36452/jmedscientiae.v2i2.2818>
- Geoepidemiology and environmental factors of psoriasis and psoriatic arthritis .. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0896841109001590>
- Zhao, P., Zhu, X., Liu , Y., Wang, B., Wang, C., & Burns , F. J. (1998, November 1). Solar Ultraviolet Radiation and Skin Damage: An Epidemiological Study among a Chinese Population. Heldref Publications, 53(6), 405-409. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00039899809605728>